

THREAT AND COPING APPRAISAL ON EARTHQUAKE READINESS AMONG INTEGRATED SCHOOL STUDENTS OF BATANGAS STATE UNIVERSITY

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ABSTRACT

The Philippines is facing increased exposure to life-threatening hazards of both natural and man-made disaster and the most susceptible to it is our young population. Thus, preparedness measures and mitigation strategies should be introduced in schools to reduce exposure and risk to the community. Past studies revealed that there are factors affecting ones' behavior during a disaster. Hence, this study was conducted to determine these factors that affect their preparedness and knowledge on earthquake among Junior and Senior High school students of Batangas State University – Integrated School. The objectives of this study are to determine the factors that may affect the preparedness of the respondents with regards to threat and coping appraisal. Related literature and studies were presented to support and obtain result. The method used was a descriptive type with a quantitative approach using survey questionnaires, with a total of two hundred twenty-nine (229) respondents. The researcher used different statistical treatment to evaluate data from the survey questionnaires. Chi-square was used to determine if there is a significant relationship between the demographic profile of the respondents and the factors affecting their knowledge to earthquake readiness and if there is a significant relationship between student's knowledge to their behavior during earthquake. According to the result of this study, among the relationship between the profile and threat appraisal, only the grade level has significant relationship on threat appraisal while in coping appraisal, age of the respondents has significant relationship to coping appraisal. There is significant relationship between threats and coping appraisal therefore, there is a significant relationship between student's knowledge about disaster preparedness and their behavior during earthquake. Lastly, the output of this study is a disaster management plan that focuses on improving the student's awareness and readiness.

Keywords: Disaster Preparedness, Earthquake Readiness, Descriptive, Philippines